

IMPLICATIONS OF DEMAND ELASTICITY ON HOUSEHOLDS FOOD DEMAND IN SOUTHWEST, NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19130474>

Keywords:
*Food, Prices,
Demand,
Households
and Elasticity*

Abstract: *The study examined the implications of rising food prices on households food demand in Southwest, Nigeria. Total of 384 households were selected using a multistage sampling technique. Primary data were collected on household's food demand and socioeconomic characteristics. Linear approximate almost ideal demand system model (LA/AIDS) was used to estimate the elasticities of households demand based on uncompensated own price elasticity. Results shows that values of own price elasticity of demand for rice and semovita had a negative sign and were > 1 (1.08 and 1.33 respectively); indicates elastic demand. This implies household's shifts their demand from rice and semovita to substitute food. Also, yam, beans and garri had own-price elasticity values that were < 1 ; 0.95, 0.09 and 0.33 respectively indicating an inelastic demand, a relatively low change in quantity demanded; yam, beans and garri is a necessity food. This study recommends that production of yam, beans and garri is worthwhile since there is a readymade market for it. Policy makers in Nigeria should create an enabling environment for its production so that these foods can be made available at affordable prices thereby increasing household welfare and improving the welfare of the economy at large in Southwest, Nigeria.*

1.2 Introduction

Food is one of the basic necessities of life that is essential for the growth, repair and maintenance of the body (1). The food baskets

included in this study are five of the major staple foods in Nigeria which includes, rice, garri, yam, beans and semovita. Prices of food is one of the major factor that determines

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British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 10; Issue: 2

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 7.94

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

households demand for food and rising prices of food have been observed to have a depressing impact on households welfare including their health and nutritional status (2).

Elasticity describes how a change in the price of goods or services affect the quantity demanded of the good or services (3) and this is evident in several studies. For instance, it was reported that in India Cereals were found to be demand elastic while high value (Proteinous food) commodities were demand elastic and that if inflation in food prices remains unabated for an extended period, there is the possibility of consumers shifting their demand to cereal dominated diet and thus resulting in under nutrition (4). It was also observed that in Pakistan, vegetables and pulses are demand inelastic while meat and fruits are demand elastic (5). Some researchers in Australia reported that rice, dairy product, pork, sugar and Jam are highly demand elastic (6). It was also observed that among Croatian's, soft drinks, vegetables and fruits, cheese and eggs, milk, cereals and bread are demand inelastic (7).

Households demand for food influences business activities because it is a major component of national income in Nigeria thus assessing the response of households to change in food prices is of importance to the economy of a country (8), Previous research work also confirms that a significant relationship exists

between households demand for food and economic development of a country (9). It has been observed that the sensitivity of household demand for food items to changes in price differs; some are highly sensitive which results in significant fall in demand while household demand for some food items are less sensitive with increase in price (5). Substitution is one of the coping strategies adopted by households to rising food prices is to shift their demand to a substitute food with lesser prices. Several researchers have estimated elasticities based on food groups but this study differs from others in the sense that it estimates elasticities of individual food items. The objective of this study was to estimate the elasticities of demand for five major staple foods in Nigeria thereby describing its implications on their demand by households.

2.0 Methods

The Southwest geopolitical zone of Nigeria, where this study was carried out is made up of six (6) States namely, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Ekiti, Lagos and Ogun States. A random selection of three States from the Southwest of Nigeria made up the study sample. The States are Ogun, Osun, and Ondo.

Primary data were used in this study. During a field study, data from households were obtained using a standardized questionnaire.

The sample for this study was chosen using a Multi-stage sampling technique to select 384

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households consuming rice in Southwest. This method was chosen as a result of earlier researchers (10) use of it to choose representative samples from big populations. Since rice is a staple food generally eaten in Nigeria, it was presumptively assumed that the population of the study area would greatly influence the number of households that would have a need for rice grains there. First three states were randomly selected (Ogun, Osun and Ondo) from the six states that made up the Southwest. The following is the formula for the proportional sampling strategy used to obtain the sample size for this study was obtained with the following formula:

$$V = Z^2 NP (1-P) / d^2 (N-1) + (Z^2 P (1-P)) \text{ -----}$$

----- (viii)

Where:

V = Sample size;

Z² = Table value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at the desired confidence level of 3.841;

N = Population size (for the three states are: Ogun (3,751,140), Osun (3,416,959) and Ondo (3,441,024) = 10,609,123 (11);

P = Population proportion which was assumed to be 50 percent of the population size; that is, 0.50;

D = Degree of accuracy was expressed as a proportion (0.05).

Therefore, the appropriate sample size that is representative of the population was estimated as:

$$V = 3.841 (10,609,123 \times 0.5) (1-0.5) / (0.05)^2$$

$$(10,609,123-1) + (3.841 \times 0.5) (1-0.5)$$

$$V = 10,187,410.3607 / 26,523.76525$$

$$V = 384.086$$

Approximately, the representative sample size, (S) chosen for this study was 384.

Also, the sample size chosen for each state (S_t) was derived as follows:

$$V_t = [\text{Population of a state} / \text{total population of the three states}] \times \text{representative sample size for the study (384)}; \text{ i.e } V_t = (P_s / T_{3s}) \times R_s \text{ -----}$$

----- (ix)

V_t = Sample size chosen for each state;

P_s = Population of a state;

T_{3s} = Representative sample size for the study (384).

Using the Marshallian (or uncompensated) and Hicksian (compensated) demand specifications, the elasticities of household demand for rice were calculated. They were derived from the further transformation of the LA/AIDS model (12). The algebraic expressions for the elasticities of households' demand for rice were specified and estimated as below (13):

(i) The uncompensated demand elasticity estimates (i.e. Marshallian elasticity, which is the price elasticity of ordinary demand for rice) were computed as follows:

Own-price elasticity (ε_{ii}^M) of rice demand,

$$\epsilon_{ii}^M = -1 + \frac{Y_{ii}}{w_i} -$$

$$\beta_i \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

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Cross-price elasticity (ϵ_{ij}^M) of rice demand,

$$\epsilon_{ij}^M = \frac{Y_{ij}}{w_i} - \beta_i \left(\frac{w_i}{w_j} \right) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

(ii) The compensated demand elasticity estimates (i.e. Hicksian elasticity of rice demand) were computed as follows:

Own-price elasticity (ϵ_{ii}^H) of rice demand,

$$\epsilon_{ii}^H = -1 + \frac{Y_{ii}}{w_i} + w_i \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Cross-price elasticity (ϵ_{ij}^H) of rice demand,

$$\epsilon_{ij}^H = \frac{Y_{ij}}{w_i} + w_j \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Where;

w_i = Budget share of i^{th} food items in the household's total food expenditure

γ_{ii} = Price coefficient for i^{th} food items in the households

3.0 Results and Discussions

3.1 Socioeconomic Characteristics of households' head

The distributions of head of household by age are presented in Table 1. Majority (67.40 per cent) of household heads in the Southwest were about 31 and 50 years old, with a mean of 45 years. This suggests that the household heads are in their active years and with the likely tendency to consume more quantities of food (i.e. calorie or energy food) to meet their daily food requirement thereby suggesting a likely positive influence on the demand for staple food (rice, beans, yam, semovita and garri). The result is consistent with previous studies which opined that the age of households' head significantly influenced food demand (14).

Table 1: Distributions of household's head by age

	Ogun state		Osun state		Ondo state		Southwest	
Age group in years	Freq.	Per cent	Freq.	Per cent	Freq.	Per cent	Freq.	Per cent
Below 30	3	2.30	5	4.80	5	4.10	13	3.60
31-50	83	63.80	73	69.50	84	69.40	240	67.40
Above 50	44	33.90	27	25.70	32	26.50	103	29.00
Total	130	100.00	105	100.00	121	100.00	356	100.00
Mean age	46		44		45		45	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

3.2 Educational status of households' head

Table 2 presents the percentage distributions of household heads by their educational attainments. This result shows that majority (90.4 per cent) of the household heads in

Southwest had a form of formal education. This is expected to have a positive effect on the preference, and hence the demand, for food. Earlier empirical studies (15) - (16) – (17) have posited that formal education of households head showed a positive effect on their households' demand for food.

Table 2: Distributions of households' head by their Educational status

Level of education	Ogun state		Osun state		Ondo state		Southwest	
	Freq.	Per cent	Freq.	Per cent	Freq.	Per cent	Freq.	Per cent
No formal education	13	10.00	10	9.52	11	9.10	34	9.60
Primary education	13	10.00	8	7.62	9	7.40	30	8.40
Secondary education	13	10.00	14	13.30	16	13.20	43	12.10
Tertiary education	91	70.00	73	69.60	85	70.30	249	69.90
Total	130	100.00	105	100.00	121	100.00	356	100.00

Source: field survey, 2020

3.3 Elasticity of Demand for food

Table 3 shows the compensated own-price elasticity of demand of the food items. All the estimates had the predicted negative sign, with the exception of beans. Since the results for the estimates were greater than one, it implies that rice ($\epsilon_{11}^H = -2.75$), yam ($\epsilon_{22}^H = -2.55$), semovita ($\epsilon_{33}^H = -2.71$), gari ($\epsilon_{44}^H = -3.93$), and beans ($\epsilon_{55}^H = 7.88$) had an elastic demand. It follows that a rise in the price of these food items will

lead to a drop in the quantity demanded by the households. Similarly, the estimations of the uncompensated own-price elasticity of demand for rice ($\epsilon_{11}^M = -1.08$) and semovita ($\epsilon_{33}^M = -1.33$) revealed an elastic demand; this means that an increase in the prices of rice and semovita will lead to 1.08% and 1.33% decrease in the quantity demanded by households. This also implies that a 1% increase in prices of rice and semovita will lead to a 1.08% and 1.33% drop in

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the quantity that will be demanded by households, thus rice and semovita are luxury good in households' food basket and it also indicates that households shifts their demand from rice and semovita to substitute food. The estimations of the uncompensated own-price elasticity of demand was in elastic demand for yam ($\epsilon_{22}^M = -0.953$), beans ($\epsilon_{55}^M = 0.092$), and garri ($\epsilon_{44}^M = 0.332$) which means that an increase in the prices of these food items will not amount to a significant decrease in the quantity demanded by households. This implies that a 1% increase in their prices will lead to a 0.95%, 0.09% and 0.33% drop in the quantity consumed or demanded by households. Since the effect of change in price leads to a relatively low change in quantity demanded; yam, beans and garri is treated as a necessity good in households' food basket. These results are in Table 3: Own-price and cross-price elasticity of demand for rice grains and selected food items for the Southwest Compensated elasticity (Hicksian)

resonance with that of earlier researchers, who found that in Nigeria, increase in the prices of cereals (rice inclusive) results in decrease in households' demand for this group of food.

The calculated results for compensated cross-price elasticity indicated that yam ($\epsilon_{21}^H = -1.681$), semovita ($\epsilon_{31}^H = -1.581$), garri ($\epsilon_{41}^H = -1.713$), and beans ($\epsilon_{51}^H = -1.674$) were complementary foods to rice in the households because of the negative sign of the coefficients. Additionally, for the uncompensated cross-price elasticity, results revealed that semovita ($\epsilon_{31}^M = 0.067$) is a substitute food item for rice in households in the Southwest, while yam ($\epsilon_{21}^M = -0.143$), garri ($\epsilon_{41}^M = -0.276$), and beans ($\epsilon_{51}^M = -0.136$) were complementary food items for rice in households because of the negative sign of the coefficients.

Rice	Yam	Semovita	Garri	Beans	
Rice	-2.755	-1.753	-1.319	-3.658	9.485
Yam	-1.681	-2.556	-1.450	-3.205	8.892
Semovita	-1.581	-1.813	-2.719	-3.215	9.328
Garri	-1.713	-1.565	-1.256	-3.939	8.472
Beans	-1.674	-1.636	-1.37	-3.193	7.877

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Uncompensated elasticity (Marshallian)

Rice	-1.086	-0.012	-0.074	-0.092	0.024
Yam	-0.143	-0.953	-0.168	0.079	0.180
Semovita	0.067	-0.095	-1.344	0.304	-0.008
Garri	-0.276	-0.06	-0.057	0.332	-0.871
Beans	-0.136	-0.032	-0.090	-0.839	0.092

Source: Field Survey, 2020

4.0 Conclusion/ Recommendation

The conclusion for this study is based on the estimations of the uncompensated elasticity of demand. An increase in the price of rice and semovita leads to a significant decrease on its demand while for yam, beans and garri, an increase in their prices does not result in a

significant decrease on its demand among households in the Southwest. From these results, this study recommends that food crop farmers in Nigeria can invest more into commercial production of yam, beans and garri since increase in their prices does not negatively affected its demand.

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